

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

POSSIBLE ANSWERS TO CONTEMPORARY CHALLENGES IN THE HEALTHCARE FINANCING SYSTEM

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Abstract

This article aims to analyze the economic challenges facing healthcare budgeting and examine potential sources of funds for sustainable financing to ensure accessibility of healthcare for the population. Healthcare financing will be examined at the macro level, encompassing the total amount of resources allocated to healthcare in society and the methods for mobilizing them. Issues related to the distribution of these resources within the healthcare system itself are beyond the scope of this paper.

Keywords: Healthcare management, financial system of healthcare, healthcare in Kazakhstan, financing of healthcare.

In the context of low economic growth and large-scale informal employment in Kazakhstan, the possibilities for increasing funding for medical care by increasing contributions from employed citizens appear to be exhausted: the tax burden on labor and production in general in Kazakhstan is currently significantly higher than in most developed countries. The reforms being implemented in the country, aimed at developing market relations, inevitably affected such a vital sector as healthcare. The primary goal of these reforms was to improve the system's efficiency, as a significant portion of its problems were caused not only and not so much by inadequate funding, but by ineffective management.

Healthcare financing has traditionally occupied a key place in health policy. However, discussions in this area have recently intensified amid the emergence of new challenges related to the global socioeconomic and political situation. The general framework for the discussion is the recognition of a developing crisis with two main characteristics. It is viewed, on the one hand, the term permacrisis has even emerged and, on the other, as multidimensional, requiring all systems of modern society to adopt new approaches to address emerging issues [1].

The chronic underfunding of the state-guaranteed program of free medical care for citizens of the Republic of Kazakhstan is a key problem in the country's healthcare system. Kazakhstan's public spending on healthcare (the compulsory medical insurance system and the state budget) is significantly lower than that of developed countries, both as a share of GDP and in absolute terms.

The healthcare system, facing several global challenges. The most serious test was the pandemic, during which, in addition to current healthcare needs, countries had to provide life-saving care to COVID-19 patients. Several public health challenges emerged, once again highlighting the importance of access to quality healthcare for the population [2].

Recently, the priority of healthcare has been raised. However, ensuring this is a complex task in today's context of new challenges. Therefore, researchers increasingly use the term "sustainable financing" of healthcare, i.e., ensuring the necessary resources to address the full range of challenges facing public healthcare systems. It should be noted that health is included in the UN Sustainable Development Goals, which provide a long-term development framework for modern countries and a benchmark for policymaking [3]. At the same time, experts acknowledge that current financing is inadequate to address public health issues, and as new challenges arise, the situation may worsen.

In analyzing healthcare financing issues, several comments are necessary. Certainly, countries differ significantly in both their overall level of socioeconomic development and their organization of public health care. Therefore, this article discusses developed countries with mature healthcare systems covering, if not all, then at least the majority of the population, which sets the general direction for the development of modern healthcare, serving as a source of best practices.

Protecting public health is one of the responsibilities of the modern state, and healthcare competes for resources with other areas of government activity. This has also manifested itself during the pandemic. Despite rhetoric about the importance of healthcare in combating the pandemic, as well as a significant increase in spending on it, data shows that the bulk of funds went to supporting the population and businesses. This is largely due to stimulus packages adopted in many countries to support various economic sectors and economic entities outside the healthcare sector.

It's worth noting that when examining healthcare financing, researchers note that:

– Higher expenditures are associated with higher life expectancy. Therefore, they are often considered one of the socioeconomic factors determining health.

– More developed countries spend more on healthcare in absolute and relative terms (expenditures as a share of GDP and government expenditures) [4].

This is certainly a general trend, although there are deviations. For example, the United States spends the most on healthcare but lags behind in life expectancy. Low-income countries such as Madagascar and Malawi spend 14 and 9 percent of their budgets on healthcare, respectively, which is comparable to developed countries. The world currently faces a challenging socioeconomic situation. The COVID-19 pandemic has caused a simultaneous health and economic crisis. In Russia, the economic restrictions used against it are an additional source of stress. The result has been an energy crisis and increased inflationary pressure. Researchers note such phenomena as rising prices, declining household incomes, declining tax revenues, growing budget deficits, and slower economic growth [5].

It should be noted that in recent years, healthcare spending in developed countries has outpaced inflation, and in 2022/2023, inflation will exceed previous years' levels in many countries. This has led to rising costs for healthcare resources and, accordingly, requires increased spending. For example, rising prices for gas, fuel, and electricity are particularly important for hospitals and emergency services. Rising labor costs have a dual impact on healthcare. On the one hand, they drive up wages in resource-producing industries, while on the other, they drive up wages in healthcare itself, which is particularly significant for healthcare as a labor-intensive industry [4]. The shortage of medical personnel was already noted before the pandemic, but the recent pandemic has led to an increased burnout among healthcare workers. Therefore, raising wages in the industry is urgent.

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which is particularly significant for healthcare as a labor-intensive industry [6]. The shortage of medical personnel was already noted before the pandemic, but the recent pandemic has led to an increased burnout among healthcare workers. Therefore, raising wages in the industry is urgent.

As a result, healthcare competes with a multitude of new public spending priorities, including defense, investments in the green economy and climate change measures, rising direct energy costs, and government support for citizens and businesses. Under these conditions, maintaining healthcare's priority in state budgets is becoming more challenging, especially as the healthcare system itself faces new challenges, including ensuring its sustainability.

Against this backdrop, the need for medical services is not decreasing; factors such as the aging population and its increasing demands, as well as technological progress, continue to operate, leading to the need to increase healthcare costs. An analysis of the discussion allows us to identify three basic scenarios, namely:

- changing the financing system itself and the relationship between its main elements (replacing tax systems with social health insurance (SHI) or vice versa);
- using additional funding sources that fit within the existing system (additional health insurance; co-payments; a tax on the consumption of goods harmful to health);
- searching for savings within the existing system in order to redistribute funding and reduce the need to increase overall healthcare spending (limiting the range of services, eliminating irrational spending).

Improving the efficiency of healthcare resource use is essential given the demand for new investments. Therefore, there is a growing need to justify additional targeted investments to create more sustainable healthcare systems, while also taking measures to reduce wasteful healthcare spending. Improving public financial management to ensure the proper use of funds and transparency in their flow can be considered as a means of achieving savings. In particular, cost analysis allows for assessing their effectiveness and ensuring a transition to more cost-effective programs.

Service rationing implies that the state funds only certain services. The problem, as with any restrictive system, is that it is difficult to determine what exactly should be included in the list of services provided. It is important not only to determine which services are selected, but also the procedures used to achieve them. A public system requires collective decision-making regarding the use of public funds. However, the requirements of economic efficiency can conflict with social and ethical considerations.

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